

INNOVATION ANALYSIS

INNOVATION DEFINITION CRITERIA ORIENTED ASESMENT OF THE FP6-IST PROJECTS

Analysis of the FP6-2002-IST-1 projects¹

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Introduction

Background information

The Sixth Framework Programme (FP6) is a strong economic development demand side instrument, which places a strong focus on innovation. All thematic activities of the programme include an innovation component.

The Information Society Technologies (IST) Work Programme is one of the priorities entirely covering ICT sector which is crucial for innovation development. A new ways of using ICT are at the origin of innovations in most products, services and processes.

For the economy, ICT are central to boosting productivity and improving the competitiveness of all businesses and industries. The ICT industry itself is one of Europe's largest economic sectors, and ICT innovations underpin progress in all other major science fields. In the public sector, ICT enable services to be delivered more efficiently, as well as new services that correspond to people's evolving needs. For society at large, ICT offer new solutions to meet societal demands. ICT is one of the few technologies - if not the only technology - with such a far reaching impact.²

Participation in programmes research activities is ensured through different instruments, among which are the 'new' Integrated Projects and 'old' Specific Targeted Research Projects/ Specific Targeted Innovation Projects STREP/ STIP (STP). All instruments containing a research and development component are required to place a special emphasis on innovation-related activities. Innovation issues must be addressed in the project proposal, and they are also taken into account during the evaluation stage and the project's implementation.

IST Strategic Objectives stresses also the new character of innovation processes: openness, with wider and faster exchange of ideas, people and resources.³

Project goals

The goal of this research was to examine innovation relevance criteria for IST thematic priority FP6 projects. During research there have been 46 IP and STP project examined as to their innovation criteria. The research yields following summary conclusions:

- Common generalization in descriptions of innovation application or implementation, very detailed technical specifications
- Dominant product innovations
- Dominant radical innovations – new process or products
- Commercialisation and market implementation is usually not included in the innovation description as an innovation activity or diffusion process
- In some of the projects Open Source model application for innovation diffusion

Other research findings were described in details in the section 5 – conclusions.

² Cordis (2005), Innovation in the Framework programmes, <http://www.cordis.lu>

³ Cordis (2005), Information Society Technologies, <http://www.cordis.lu/ist/>

Case studies and project analysis in this research concerns Sixth Framework Programme, which focuses on Community activities in the field of research, technological development and demonstration (RTD) for the period 2002 to 2006, Information Society Technologies thematic objective.

Contract and Project Management module (CPM) window

Figure 1

Research was conducted by the use of the Contract and Project Management module (CPM) of the 2006 FP6-IT system. Its aim is to assist the EC Personnel (e.g. Project and Financial officers, Head of Unit, etc.) in the day-to-day management of RTD

related contracts. CPM contains data on already negotiated and decided proposals that are ready-to-be-signed, and finishes with project closure and evaluation. Therefore, it covers the contract generation, and the whole lifecycle of a project after the contract is signed, including financial transactions.

Key services offered by CPM include:

- 1) The preparation, validation and automatic generation of FP6 contracts.
- 2) The recording and monitoring of various categories of project related events (e.g. meetings, workshops, deliverables, payments, etc.).

3) The preparation, validation, execution and monitoring of all financial transactions (e.g. commitment, payment, recovery order) required during the life-cycle of an FP6 project.

4) Advanced Search functionality that allows performing (potentially complex) queries and summary reports.

The research was executed using CPM system, which allows extracting electronic documents related to a project (i.e. Contract and its annexes, the project deliverables, cost statements and audit certificates, meetings minutes), which are stored and transparently retrieved to/from the Electronic library.

FP6-2002-IST-1 contract distribution by instrument⁴

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 2

Research consisted of examining signed contracts (technical annexes to the contract) in regards to Information Society Technology priority Call 1 (FP6-2002-IST-1). Sampling covered 50% percent of the IP (29 contracts) and 18% of the STP (17 contracts) in population of 46 contracts, totally. These two instruments (IP, STP) were chosen because of their innovation-oriented deliverables.

The structure of the analysis in the research was based on the Negotiation Guidance Noted of Coordinators of Integrated Projects (IP) and Specific Targeted Research Projects or Specific Targeted Innovation Projects (STREP, STIP). The information about innovation factor of the project is contained mainly in the Potential Impact information as well as Proposal Summary and Relevance to the objectives with the Information Society Technology (IST) priority, namely chapters describing:

- innovation-related activities
- research/ innovation components (major elements or blocks of work).

⁴ NoE – Networks of Excellence, IP – Integrated Projects, CA – Coordinated Actions, STP (STREP) Specific Targeted Research Projects, SSA- Specific Support Action

- scientific and technical (S&T) approach, which provides in detail the work planned to achieve the objectives of the project for the full duration of the project
- research, technological development and innovation related activities
- plans for management of knowledge and intellectual property and a description of the use of results (further research or exploitation)
- plan for disseminating knowledge beyond the consortium
- relevance of the objectives of the IST priority/ activity objectives
- reinforcing competitiveness or on solving societal problems or addressing specific problems

Geographical distribution analysis revealed that, even for the small sample as in this research high participation of the big, developed European countries, as France, Spain, Germany, Italy and United Kingdom is visible. There is very low participation of the EU, new member countries and third countries, with the exception of Norway.

**Spatial distribution of the projects (total number of projects)
Percentage share of the projects realized by country and instrument**
Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 3

FP6-2002-IST-1 project contract data

Majority of the projects accounts for northern and western part of the Europe. Further analysis is needed to determine detailed relation of the project distribution with state (GDP, Industry, R&D etc.). All project analysed were described as to state of art for the end of the year 2003 (3rd quarter).

Primary analysis of projects' consortium structure (size and spatial distribution of project participators) revealed that Denmark, Sweden, Germany and Belgium on average account for biggest consortium size. This indicator is an approximate measure for the innovation network size, which in further examining could determine network efficiency and added value⁵. It is interesting that biggest European states like France or Spain or Italy though having biggest number of proposals filed and potentially biggest networks (cumulated values of participants in all the proposals filed) submitted to average measures are not dominating players in network of cooperations.

Average size of consortium as an approximate measure of the innovation network chain added value. Population sample $n= 46$ projects
 Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data **Figure 4**

⁵According to *Metcalfe's law* the value of a network is approximately the square of its size (N^2). Therefore a network that doubles in size will be four times as valuable because there are four times as many exchanges that can occur due to the larger number of interconnections. Since a network user cannot connect to itself, the actual calculation is: $N(N-1)$, or $N^2 - N$.

Innovation analysis for the project was conducted in accordance with Oslo Manual guidelines - The Measurement of Scientific and Technological Activities, Proposed Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Technological Innovation Data,⁶ agreed by OECD, European Commission and Eurostat. The document embraces main theoretical aspects of modern innovation theory – especially parts that are well established and explored. It refers Cline and Rosenberg Chain link model⁷ which stresses the importance of non-linearity in the innovation processes and Schumpeterian innovation theory⁸ which stresses the importance of innovation commercialization phase. It also gives substantial background for innovation activities classification (factors influencing innovation), diffusion of innovation, defining and measuring innovation.

According to the manual **Technological product and process (TPP) innovations** *comprise implemented technologically new products and processes and significant technological improvements in products and processes. A TPP innovation has been implemented if it has been introduced on the market (product innovation) or used within a production process (process innovation). TPP innovations involve a series of scientific, technological, organisational, financial and commercial activities. The TPP innovating firm is one that has implemented technologically new or significantly technologically improved products or processes during the period under review.*⁹

Whereas the product innovation is clearly distinguished, definition of the process innovation in some cases can occur problematic. According to Oslo Manual **technological process innovation** *is the adoption of technologically new or significantly improved production methods, including methods of product delivery.*

⁶ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

⁷ Kline, S.J., N. Rosenberg (1986), "An Overview of Innovation", in Landau, R. and N. Rosenberg (eds.), The Positive Sum Strategy. Harnessing Technology for Economic Growth, National Academy Press, Washington, DC

⁸ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts

⁹ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

*These methods may involve changes in equipment, or production organisation, or a combination of these changes, and may be derived from the use of new knowledge. The methods may be intended to produce or deliver technologically new or improved products, which cannot be produced or delivered using conventional production methods, or essentially to increase the production or delivery efficiency of existing products.*¹⁰

This definition as for current state of art is currently under revision and two additional dimensions for innovation will be added to future innovation surveys: marketing innovation and organisational innovation. Above definition does not embrace organisational, managerial activities and ones that are not of technological character and can not be directly measured or associated with an output (are hard to quantify within any economic indicator).

The research did not concentrated only on the Oslo Manual innovation parameters but also as the project examining processes continued, included other categories (presence of synergies, market or social orientation of the project, managerial and organisational outcomes). Due to the small sample (46 projects) and time constraints, the analysis did not enter into deeper examination of the innovation definition features. Research revealed that projects' content could also yield additional categories, such as: innovation dissemination process, innovation output analysis, innovation recipient and timeframe of the project.

The research methodology for innovation definition analysis relied on the (Annex II) innovation analysis comparative assessment paper. Although general division of the innovation definition (stripping definition into particle elements) could be applied here, this research was enriched by other elements and findings (e.g. innovation activities and subcategories).

¹⁰ *ibid.*

Innovation Types Degree of the Innovativeness

Innovation Types

This research was designed to stay in accordance with the collection of specific innovations data (usually a “significant innovation” of some kind, or the main innovation for a firm) – which embraces the “object approach” and stands in accordance with TPP definition but also explores other innovation properties, examining whether technological criteria match, specified by guidelines).

Type of innovation (total number)

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 5

On the innovation type level, three aspects were compared: product or service innovation, process innovation and technological properties of the innovation (its technological definition in the project).

Majority of the projects examined proved to be product or service innovation oriented (85%) and strong technologically defined (74%). Process innovations accounted for 23% of the projects, totally. In some instances due to the ambiguous description, overlapping between categories occurred, what caused outrun in the percentage ratios.

ATHENA¹¹ project is an example of product/ service technological innovation. Innovation type characteristics for the project were defined as: “European

¹¹ ATHENA (2003), Advanced Technologies for Interoperability of Heterogeneous Enterprise Networks and their Applications, IST-2002-507849

research initiative in IT to remove barriers to Interoperability, to transfer and apply the research results in industrial sectors, and to foster a new ICT-enabled networked business culture.”

ECOLEAD¹² project was considered as process innovation, which innovation type was defined as: “to significantly impact in the industrial competitiveness and societal mechanisms, by providing means to effectively exploit opportunities deriving from the deployment of Collaborative Networked Organisations (CNOs), and by designing and enabling new professional work paradigms, capable of enacting the Knowledge-based Society throughout Europe”

Due to the fact that there is no clear innovation systematisation reference in the project guidelines process of determining innovation type created some problems (determination of the innovation type was supported by the project activities and project results data contained in the project potential impact chapter).

In further research technological profile of the innovation was determined. In order to precisely conduct that part, correlation between all categories of the innovation type was calculated.

Correlation between innovation type and its technological characteristics Table 1
Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

	Product or service	Process	Technology focused (TPP)	No of projects	% of instances applicable (total)
IP	X		X	16	55%
STP	X		X	15	88%
TOTAL	X		X	31	67%
IP		X	X	5	17%
STP		X	X	1	6%
TOTAL		X	X	6	13%

This analysis showed that product innovation projects accounts for 67% of total projects, strongly depending on the technological issues. MORE MORE¹³ project is an example of such project. Its aim was defined as: “Developing Extreme Ultra Violet Lithography (EUVL), the next generation technology chosen by the semiconductor industry to manufacture integrated circuits in 2010 and beyond.”

¹² EOCLEAD (2004), European Collaborative networked Organizations LEADership initiative, IST-2002-506958

This project is strongly product innovation oriented (innovation here is not a part of the production process but has a character of a final product) and produces tangible technology i.e. innovative microprocessor design (technology is not related organisational, marketing or management solutions).

GOODFOOD¹⁴ is an example of technological process innovation where its aim depends on: *“developing the new generation of analytical methods based on Micro and Nanotechnology (MST and M&NT) solutions for the safety and quality assurance along the food chain in the agrofood industry.”* This type of projects accounts for 13% of the innovations examined in the research.

Research results were also submitted to the mathematical correlation analysis. The conditional count analysis confirmed that 67% of the product or service innovation (majority) was defined as technological whereas process innovation accounted for 13%. The average measure showed smaller differences between values of both categories, but this measure is less precise and here can be used for comparison measurements.

Mathematical justification for the correlation in the innovation type

Table 2

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

(0,1) binary test	arithmetic average ¹⁵	number of instances for expected value=2	conditional count ¹⁶
Product or service	1,61	31	67%
Process	1,00	6	13%

Basic prediction analysis and elasticity analysis confirmed domination of the technological product or service innovation.

Due to the fact that research results are of discrete character, linear regression analysis was hard to conduct. Coefficiency ratio analysis - and trend line comparison - was done as an approximation measurement for whole population values (92 instances).

The analysis was claimed to be valid at the high $Rsq (>0,5)$. Relation of the elasticity (pace change) in the trend curves is proportional.

¹³ MORE MORE, (2003), Exploring new limits to Moore's law, IST-2002-507754

¹⁴ GOODFOOD (2003), Food Safety and Quality Monitoring with Microsystems, IST-2002-508774

¹⁵ Arithmetic average of the discrete values for whole population <1,2>. Average close to 2 indicates high overall correlation average equals 1 indicates no overall correlation.

Projected number in types of innovation and number of technological innovations

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 6

Elasticity ratio for the coefficient linear regression between product and service innovation and strong technological focus in it for whole population ($2 \times 46 = 92$ projects) is 1,15. The coefficient approximation of $a = 0,82$ shows that increase in this innovation category was higher than increase in their technological feature ($a = 0,68$). It means that as the number of examined projects increases their technological focus is still high (product or service category innovation is likely to be strong technology oriented). This type of innovation will be more likely to be of production or service technology development rather than managerial or organisational. For every 8 projects 7 were production or service technology oriented.

Examination of the process-oriented innovations shows significantly lower results in elasticity ratio (0,36). This indicates that for approximately every 3 projects only 1 was of strong technological characteristics. Process-based innovations are likely to be mostly managerial and organisational characteristic oriented (non TPP). They are in significant minority of examined projects and they are likely to continue to be as the research sample increases.

The statistical analysis reveals that product oriented innovations are in majority. This can be also confirmed by the general analysis of each project. Most of them

¹⁶ Conditional count for the sums of values in whole population. If sum in single instance equals 2 than correlation is said to be significant. Result indicates percentage value for the number of significantly valid correlations in whole population.

are of very technical character. Innovation results are described as the set of technology oriented deliverables: *B3G Radio System*, *PLC power line communication*, *open architecture based on common network protocol IPv6*, *Extreme Ultra Violet Lithography (EUVL)*, with very detailed specialized technical description. The overall impression reading most of the projects is that they are fitting more into the engineer specification template rather than managerial business plan or any kind of economic analysis.

Degree of the innovativeness

Generally the innovation theory distinguishes between two forms as to the degree of the innovation: radical and incremental. Oslo Manual¹⁷ systematizes this approach dividing innovations into: new products or processes, improvements in products or processes:

A technologically new product is a product whose technological characteristics or intended uses differ significantly from those of previously produced products. Such innovations can involve radically new technologies, can be based on combining existing technologies in new uses, or can be derived from the use of new knowledge. **A technologically improved product** is an existing product whose performance has been significantly enhanced or upgraded. A simple product may be improved (in terms of better performance or lower cost) through use of higher-performance components or materials, or a complex product which consists of a number of integrated technical sub-systems may be improved by partial changes to one of the sub-systems.¹⁸

The research revealed that most of the projects accounted for radical innovations (67%) and due to overlapping in the categories, 41% of the projects were of incremental innovation character.

Due to their complexity, some of the projects included both types of innovations these accounted for 9% of all projects. Table below shows correlation distribution for all projects.

¹⁷ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

¹⁸ *ibid.*

Degree of the innovativeness

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Table 3

	New product or process	Improvements in product or process	No of projects	% of instances applicable
IP		X	10	22%
STP		X	5	11%
TOTAL		X	15	33%
IP	X		18	39%
STP	X		9	20%
TOTAL	X		27	59%
IP	X	X	1	2%
STP	X	X	3	7%
TOTAL	X	X	4	9%

Under this analysis 33% projects alone (15 projects) of the product or/and process innovations did not have radical character - was based on already existing technology in comparison to 59% of strongly radical projects.

Degree of Innovativeness

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 7

The analysis revealed that level of sophistication of the project proposals as to innovation added value is very high (IPs account for bigger number radical innovations). Probability determinant for creating radical innovation has not been established and

requires further analysis (there could exist correlation between this criterion and the size of consortium or character of the organisations in the consortium).

The example of the radical innovation is MORE MORE¹⁹ project: “*Extreme Ultra Violet Lithography (EUVL), the next generation technology chosen by the semiconductor industry to manufacture integrated circuits in 2010 and beyond.*” Its principal objective is to “*Push the boundaries of current technological*

¹⁹ MORE MORE, (2003), Exploring new limits to Moore’s law, IST-2002-507754

capability in the EUVL domain and develop new technology and processes which have already demonstrated that they profoundly impact the economic fabric of society, including the material and human environment. They also largely influence the competitive position of Europe in the wider world. The pursuit of innovation is therefore the fundamental raison-d'être of this proposal."

OBAN²⁰ is an example of incremental innovation creation, which bases on building up innovation added value for already existing solutions. OBAN is an: *"innovative approach to establish a broadband mobile network in line with present B3G visions. The concept is based upon an Open Access Network (OAN) approach characterised by that: 1) all private wireless LANs and broadband access lines are made available for public use, thus the stationary users (the hosts) can continue to use their wireless LAN as before 2) casual passing users can access and maintain communication via these access points. To realise the concept existing protocols and mechanisms have to undergo fundamental improvements and the following sub-objectives are therefore identified. Each of them contains innovative R&D aspects: 1) To develop/adapt access control and security mechanisms, 2) To develop/adapt appropriate mobility functionalities, 3) To develop/adapt appropriate QoS mechanisms, 4) To explore relevant legal and regulatory issue, 5) To explore/simulate the potential network coverage."*

Innovativeness degree correlation analysis revealed that new product innovations are in the majority of the projects. This result confirmed the hypothesis that radical innovations are more often presented in the projects.

Product or service innovation characteristics

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Table 4

(0,1) binary test	arithmetic average	number for expected value=2	conditional count
New product	1,521	27	59%
Improvements in product	1,260	14	35%
New process	0,913	7	15%
Improvements in process	0,652	4	9%

According to conditional count analysis, 59% of the innovations were radical (new) product innovations whereas this is the case for only 15% of process

²⁰ OBAN (2003), Open Broadband Access Networks IST-2002-001889

innovations. 35% of the product innovations and 9% of the process innovations had character of improvements, but in all cases these were accompanied by new product or process. In every single project incremental process innovation was accompanied by another innovation, concerned as radical.

Prediction and dynamism analysis did not reveal any radical results. It confirmed domination of the product and radical innovations overtime (as the sample increases). The dynamism in number increase of product innovations is radically higher than for process innovations.

Types of innovation – projection, Number of radical and marginal innovations

Figure 8

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Orientation in the innovation projects –the recipient of the innovation

Research examined several criteria for the innovation socio-economic orientation. To establish these criteria research identified innovation recipient destination group. This information allowed to establish whether innovation was socially or market oriented and whether this criterion was narrowly or generally defined.

Research revealed that most of the innovation recipient (65%) were socially oriented and generally defined. Due to the category overlapping 54% of the projects were market oriented and 35% from all of the projects were narrowly defined as to the innovation recipient.

List below shows examples of the narrow innovation recipient definitions, identified in some projects: *The customers' way of life and rendering of services, Operators' operation and usage of the network infrastructure, Manufacturers' delivery of new innovative products, service providers' way of providing services and content to the public wherever and whenever; or European Automotive Industry* to very wide: *Information Society, users, citizens, Knowledge-based Society throughout Europe.*

The example of the project with very narrow innovation recipient definition is LASAGNE²¹. It enumerates innovation recipients as follows: “ • *residential users: wide access to knowledge data bases, tele-learning, tele-working, on-line entertainment, interactive games, tele-surveillance and e-commerce.*

- *public organisations: large data exchanges required in advance social and administrative services, tele-medicine, special event coverage, better security of persons.*
- *enterprises: efficient data exchange (Intranet), to open the boundaries in the case of a multinational company, e-commerce, leading to a better efficiency of work”*

Clear description of the innovation recipient allows identifying sector of the economy for the innovation to be implemented. Analysis of the sector for the innovation implementation is valuable information as innovation impact and its potential may vary sectorwise.

²¹ LASAGNE (2003), All-optical label swapping employing optical logic gates in network nodes, IST-2002-507509

Detailed correlation analysis revealed that 54 % of the projects define strong market oriented innovation deliverables, out of which 36% are generally defined. 65 % of the cases are socially oriented innovation and almost 67% of socially oriented definitions point to very general recipient. 13% of all projects were defined in very general way because of their general coverage of both social and economic goals.

Recipient definition and generalization in the definition

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Table 5

	Market oriented	Social oriented	Is defined generally?	No of projects	no of total cases applicable for the assumption	% of total cases applicable	% of applicable cases complying with the condition	% of total
IP	X		X	6	16	55%	38%	21%
STP	X		X	3	9	53%	33%	18%
TOTAL	X		X	9	25	54%	36%	20%
IP		X	X	13	19	66%	68%	45%
STP		X	X	7	11	65%	64%	41%
TOTAL		X	X	20	30	65%	67%	43%
IP	X	X	X	4	29	100%	14%	14%
STP	X	X	X	2	17	100%	12%	12%
TOTAL	X	X	X	6	46	100%	13%	13%

General conclusion for this analysis is that majority of the projects are very generally defined as to innovation recipient and there is a stronger generalization tendency in socially oriented proposals than in economic (market oriented projects tend to list tangible quantifiable deliverables).

Innovation activities
Innovation dissemination
Innovation outputs

Innovation activities

According to the Oslo Manual²² innovation activities comprise of: *R&D, other acquisition of knowledge (patents, licences, technical services, etc.), acquisition of machinery and equipment (both incorporating new technology and for standard use when producing a new product), various other preparations for production/delivery, including tooling up, staff training, etc., and marketing.*

Research aim was as the project examining process continued to dynamically develop, and categorize innovation activities also out of the list. Research identified categories not included directly in the OECD's innovation measurement methodology. The innovation activities list include following categories: Technology creation and development, Research, Integrative activities. These subdivide into specialized: technological activities, organisational activities, commercial activities and financial activities.

²² OECD (1997), Oslo Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

Major innovation activities

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 10

Majority of the projects (82%) define innovation activities as technological activities. Research (54%) and Integrative (21%) activities were also considered as significant. On the instrument level Integrated Projects (IP) produced more integrative activities whereas Specific Targeted Research Projects (STP) were dominated by technological innovations.

Innovation activities

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 11

Under detailed analysis research confirmed that innovation activities are mostly of technological character (85%). Scientific research activities accounted for 39% and organisational activities for 26% of all projects. Commercial activities - pushing innovation into marketing process - were defined as a part of innovation process only in 15% of the projects.

Examined projects brought many examples of technological activities, as majority of them tend to list new or improved technologies and processes, which comprised on innovation. MIMOSA²³ project exemplifies describes innovation activities as: *“Wireless Remote Powered Sensor +µbattery; Microphone array Proof of concept; Inertial User Interface IC Prototypes; Monochrome VGA Microprojector; Low-cost Packaging”*

AGAMENNON²⁴ is an example of the project defining scientific and commercial innovation activities: *“Besides the specific advances and innovative features and technologies that characterize Agamemnon, the project contribution to innovation lies also in: - Innovative exploitation of 3G mobile phones already owned by the visitors capabilities in order to; Integrated approach, on a technological perspective, to address the three main areas of interest in Cultural ; - An immediately exploitable concept, that delivers a truly usable educational service with limited capital investment; - An innovative business model for the archaeological sites -No upfront infrastructure investments and Profits coming from airtime revenue sharing agreements with network operators”*

PRIME²⁵ project defines scientific activities as well as integrative innovation activities as: *“Development of Integrated framework for the establishment and operation of collaborative networked organizations (CNO), providing platforms for VO Breeding Environments, Dynamic Virtual Organizations, and Professional Virtual Communities.- Significant contribution to increasing both the public knowledge and the actual implantation of collaborative networks in the society.”*

TPP innovation definition stresses importance of the commercialization in the innovation activities: *A technological product innovation is the implementation/commercialisation of a product with improved performance characteristics such as to deliver objectively new or improved services to the consumer.*²⁶

Results for this part of the research revealed relatively low percentage of commercialisation activities (15%) included in the innovation definition. This confirms very strong focus of the projects on the technological and scientific

²³ MIMOSA (2003), Microsystems platform for Mobile Services and Applications, IST-2002-507045

²⁴ AGAMENNON (2003), Pictures from the Past: A Wireless Network of Magical Digital Cameras and Palmtops for Archaeological Travels Through Time , IST-2002-508013

²⁵ PRIME (2004), Privacy and Identity Management for Europe , IST-2002-507591

²⁶ OECD (1997), Oslo manual

technical goals, rather than economic and managerial characteristics of the innovation.

Commercialisation as an integral part of the innovation development was generally under-addressed in the projects.

Knowledge dissemination process – diffusion of the innovation

Diffusion of the innovation can be defined as: the way, in which innovations spread, through market or non-market channels, from first implementation anywhere in the world, to other countries and regions and to other industries/markets and firms.²⁷

Research identified following channels for innovation diffusion:

- Cooperation,
- Publications, Press Releases, Reports, Workshops, Conferences,
- Electronic means e.g.: databases, websites, wide deployment of network applications,
- Commercial marketing, promotion (events, competitions),
- Project patents, licensing, intellectual property protection,
- Open Source model

It is assumed that as a result of the diffusion process, innovation can either be further implemented (not only as a market product but also as a general knowledge about technology or scientific object), or undergo innovative improvements (such scheme is particularly characteristic for the open source model)

Although the cooperation is one of the most important characteristics of the FP6 projects, its clear importance as an innovation diffusion factor was stressed in almost 80% of the projects (78%). The cooperation is a dominating channel for the innovation diffusion in the reviewed projects.

Classical knowledge dissemination means such as: Publications, Press Releases, Reports, Workshops, Conferences; and Electronic means (e.g. databases, websites, wide deployment of network applications) account for 76% and 63% of all projects.

Commercial marketing and promotion (direct market oriented diffusion) accounts for 33% of the innovations. This indicator shows comparatively poor market orientation of the projects.

Patenting of the project results accounts for 11% of all cases. According to the theory, patents are used to track the level of diffusion of knowledge across technology areas, countries, sectors, firms, etc., and the level of internationalisation of innovative activities. Patent indicators can serve to measure the output of R&D, its productivity, structure and the development of a specific technology/industry.²⁸

The most interesting channel identified in the projects, though least common (11%) is the open source model²⁹.

As an example, GST³⁰ project defines exploitation and dissemination activities as aimed at spreading awareness and information beyond the research community. *“Embryonic community: after a development kit is made available a community of analyst (business and technical) and developers will be created. The community will be started via the open source community or via involvement of SMEs, schools and universities. Within the community, GST will help the community members to exchange information and implementations. The community will be provided with controlled access to a genuine telematics infrastructure for validated services.”*

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ OECD (2004) , Compendium on Patent Statistics, OECD Publishing, Paris

²⁹ Analysis and theoretical background of the Open Source model was described in: Innovation Conceptualization and Innovation New Models Theoretical Summary, Szmytkowski Daniel (2005), Brussels. This paper is a practical continuation of this paper which is of a theoretical nature.

³⁰ GST (2003), Global System for Telematics enabling On-line Safety Services, IST-2002-507033

B-BONE³¹ project defines knowledge dissemination, mostly concentrating on classical diffusion channels: *“The results of the project will be published in appropriate workshops and conferences and magazines. Two main vehicles of knowledge dissemination will be particularly set up during the duration of the project and even beyond its lifetime. The first is a web page where a public and a private area will be defined where all the project information can be accessed in a very convenient way. The second will be the organisation of a public workshop with participation of other IST projects, but not limited to. The main project results will be presented at this workshop.”*

Innovation Outputs

Innovation outputs as an element of the innovation definition is especially strongly visible in the US frameworks³². This is not distinguishing for the OECD

³¹ B-BONE (2003), BROADCASTING AND MULTICASTING OVER ENHANCED UMTS MOBILE BROADBAND NETWORKS, IST-2002-507607

³² Institute of Standards and Technology (2003), Between Invention and Innovation, an Analysis of Funding for Early-Stage Technology Development, NIST GCR 02–841, <http://www.atp.nist.gov/eao/gcr02-841/chapt2.htm>, Massachusetts;

Council on Competitiveness, Donofrio Nick (2004), 21th century Innovation Working Group Final Report, Innovation The new reality for national Prosperity, National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC

and EC innovation definition framework (reviewed here). In the research, innovation outputs/results were grouped into following general categories:

- Qualitative outcomes (e.g. diminishing digital divide, improved service quality, comparable change in standard of living)
- Quantitative outcomes (economic indicator change i.e.: job growth, GDP change, industrial production, demand/supply change, etc.)

More detailed group of innovation results included:

- Input to technical standards,
- Cost efficiency – cost reductions,
- Integration – synergies
- Improved management and organisational processes.

Innovation Outputs

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 13

The analysis revealed that due to the programme criteria and proposal template requirements (programme proposers are required to indicate project's impact on the technical standards), every examined project show strong technical focus (100%).

Qualitative innovation outcomes accounted for 73% of all examined projects (e.g. *improved working conditions, positive impact on natural environment, stronger relation ties with (inter)national research organisations*³³). Quantitative innovation outcomes were identified in 50% of the projects. (e.g. *integrating services*

³³ SHIFT (2003), Smart High-Integration Flex Technologies, IST-2002-507745

facilitating efficient use of services, easy access to information, cost-effective network solutions based on innovative architectures³⁴)

Cost efficiency, integration and synergies, improved managerial and organisational processes accounted respectively for 28%, 26% and 7% of all proposals.

In general outputs/results of the innovation comprise on the substantially important part of the project. Potential impact of the project, mostly focus on contribution to standards, policy development, risk assessment and communication strategy. There is lack of strong market oriented definitions of actions undertaken and plans (e.g. projects include: *Plan for using and disseminating knowledge, Gender Action Plan, Raising public participation and awareness*). Innovation is presented as a technical and technological output and their results are very technological oriented. While cost efficiency is quite easy to identify, added value form integration and improved management is less recognized throughout the projects.

Timeframe of the projects

Timeframe (project live cycle) of the project is an important for identifying innovation validity and its up-to-date criteria as in some sectors innovations can devaluate quicker than in other (this is true in the ICT sector which still expands rapidly).

Average live time for IP project for was 36 months and for STP 30 months. Overall average for all projects was 34 months. Almost 3-year period for an innovation to be designed constructed and implemented could be relatively long time. To examine that problem more detailed analysis is needed.

³⁴ BROADWAN (2003), Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks, IST-2002-001930

Methodology summary

Examination of the projects (technical Annexes I to the project contract) presented substantial difficulty in extracting required information. Although there exists strict guideline as to the structure of the document, which indicates precisely where innovation characteristics are located (most of the information is contained in the potential impact section), often project descriptions did not contain direct innovation description. In that case project summary, project objectives, relevance to the objectives and outline implementation plan needed to be reviewed.

There also appeared problem of the ambiguity of examined criteria. This caused frequent overlaps –in some cases especially visible, because of the generalizations in the descriptions. It could be also observed that projects were written in very formal way.

In general, reviewed material presents good and detailed description of the potential innovation. Projects are a very valuable database of the existing innovative technologies (as a majority of projects, presented strict technological character) that presents unique value for further research.

Research findings Innovation activities

6th Framework Programme projects for Information Society Technologies thematic priority, represents very specific group of innovation projects, subjected to strict regulations and rules. Projects are not free designed but rather are presentation of technological potential put in frames of technical specifications.

Analysis revealed that the most dominant innovation category is product or service innovation (84%), which is mostly of critical character: 67% (rather than incremental: 41%). Other innovation categories (process innovation and marginal improvements in product or process), in most of the cases, accompanied the most dominant group of product and radical innovations.

It is justified by strict rules for constructing project contents. Product innovation could be more characteristic for the industry and manufacturing sector (e.g. product being industrial prototype). Market implementation potentially transfers the product into applicable market good distributed in other sector of economy – service sector. This is characteristic for IST projects which concern Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).

Justification for statistical domination of the product innovations is that product innovations are more 'visible', and more easily extracted from general innovation description, as well as better understood in common sense. If there is a process innovation identified (innovation as a part of the production process, not as a final product), it will be distinctively connected with the integration activities (e.g. ECOLEAD³⁵), cooperation and organisational (e.g. ATHENA³⁶) innovation.

The most interesting finding of the research is a lack of recognition of the commercial activities (market implementation) as an immanent part of the innovation process. Commercialisation was defined as directly contained within innovation process, only for 15% of the projects (7 projects out of 46 totally). The innovation diffusion process analysis showed that commercial marketing and promotion (market oriented diffusion) account for 33% of all projects. This

³⁵ ECOLEAD (2004), European Collaborative networked Organizations LEADership initiative, IST-2002-506958

³⁶ ATHENA (2003), Advanced Technologies for Interoperability of Heterogeneous Enterprise Networks and their Applications, IST-2002-507849

indicates that market orientation is better recognised at the innovation diffusion process level (knowledge dissemination).

The analysis results, suggest that majority of the projects are **market push oriented** innovation, comprising of: preliminary research, applied engineer research, implementation, marketing.

The linearity of the innovation development is another aspect, which maybe not dominant, but in some cases visible in the projects. Even though project guidelines (project detailed implementation plan – chapter 8) provide option for describing potential non linearity in the innovation creation process, there is a tendency to flatter (line out) the processes that covers innovation development processes, (planning and timetable is mostly characterized by GANT chart rather than by model that allows randomness in activity completion times - Network analysis tool omitted in some of the projects³⁷: Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT)). Potential linearity in the projects implementation plan could be exemplified by following table:

Linearity in projects' implementation plan

Source: CPM, FP6-2002-IST-1 contract data

Figure 13

Project acronym	Analysis and assessment	Specification	Designing, development	Validation refinement	Deployment, results dissemination
WINNER	1		2	3	
OPERA		1	2	3	4
DAIDALOS	1		2	3	
PRIME	1		2		3

* number represents sequence of the process in the project implementation plan

Another interesting aspect of the innovation diffusion process, concerned the open source model. The open source model, as an user oriented innovation model, provides additional channel for innovation development. In summary,

³⁷ e.g. MYHEART project (MYHEART (2003), MyHeart-Fighting cardio-vascular diseases by preventive lifestyle & early diagnosis, IST-2002-507816)

following characteristics can be applied to the open source innovation development model:

- non linearity (star shaped topology -network relational)
- marginal/ incremental added value in innovation build-up process
- free results: zero costs of the final product, guaranteed by license

BRICKS³⁸ described as an open project, is an example of the project using open source model for knowledge dissemination process: 1) *its use of **open standards** and the **open source** software development approach;* 2) *it is based on an **open community** to enlarge and enforce its resources and input from researchers, scientists, art professionals and users;* 3) *it is **open** to expansion, by inserting new application scenarios and other project results in a "plug and play" manner.*

As an conclusion, it is interesting that projects being big hierarchically organised, consortia, seek for the additional spin-offs that target dispersed innovation network outside the boundaries of the consortium and not fitting in their internal management structure. It is certainly very positive impulse for innovation diffusion process, which may lead to more efficient marginal innovation process (more frequent improvements).

Annex 3 summarises research statistical results.

Following points summarise overall conclusions of the research:

- Common generalization in descriptions of innovation application or implementation, very detailed technical specifications
- Dominant product innovations
- Dominant radical innovations – new process or products
- Commercialisation and market implementation is usually not included in the innovation description as an innovation activity or diffusion process
- Usage of Open Source model for innovation diffusion in some projects

³⁸ BRICKS (2003), Building Resources for Integrated Cultural Knowledge Services, IST-2002-507457

Follow up

Although research delivered some interesting conclusions it presents some downsides as to its methodology and problem coverage, which could be seen as challenging goal for the follow up and future research. The main problem of the project that occurred, was sampling. Increase in a number of the projects examined could deliver more representative conclusions.

Project also did not address problem of quantifiable innovation measures on the proposal level (micro scale). Research developed own innovation analysis framework relying on the OECD, EC and EUROSTAT methodology towards *Measurement of Scientific and Technological Activities, Proposed Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Technological Innovation Data*.

This approach could be expanded by confronting used methodology (Oslo Manual oriented) to other existing "innovation measurement" frameworks.

In regards to the most interesting findings of the research, the follow up could concentrate on the examination and validation of the results for the market orientation in the innovations as well as usage of the open source model for the innovation diffusion (including indicator development as well as efficiency – input/output analysis).

References

List of projects summarised

- AGAMENNON (2003), Pictures from the Past: A Wireless Network of Magical Digital Cameras and Palmtops for Archaeological Travels Through Time, IST-2002-508013
- ATHENA (2003), Advanced Technologies for Interoperability of Heterogeneous Enterprise Networks and their Applications, IST-2002-507849
- B-BONE (2003), BROADCASTING AND MULTICASTING OVER ENHANCED UMTS MOBILE BROADBAND NETWORKS, IST-2002-507607
- BRICKS (2003), Building Resources for Integrated Cultural Knowledge Services, IST-2002-507457
- BROADWAN (2003), Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks, IST-2002-001930
- ECOLEAD (2004), European Collaborative networked Organizations LEADership initiative, IST-2002-506958
- GOODFOOD (2003), Food Safety and Quality Monitoring with Microsystems, IST-2002-508774
- GST (2003), Global System for Telematics enabling On-line Safety Services, IST-2002-507033
- LASAGNE (2003), All-optical label swapping employing optical logic gates in network nodes, IST-2002-507509
- MIMOSA (2003), Microsystems platform for Mobile Services and Applications, IST-2002-507045
- MORE MORE, (2003), Exploring new limits to Moore's law, IST-2002-507754
- MYHEART (2003), MyHeart-Fighting cardio-vascular diseases by preventive lifestyle & early diagnosis, IST-2002-507816
- OBAN (2003), Open Broadband Access Networks, IST-2002-001889
- PRIME (2004), Privacy and Identity Management for Europe, IST-2002-507591
- SHIFT (2003), Smart High-Integration Flex Technologies, IST-2002-507745

Publications

Council on Competitiveness, Donofrio Nick (2004), 21th century Innovation Working Group Final Report, Innovation The new reality for national Prosperity, National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC

Cordis (2005), Innovation in the Framework programmes, <http://www.cordis.lu>

Cordis (2005), Information Society Technologies, <http://www.cordis.lu/ist/>

FP6, NEGOTIATION GUIDANCE NOTES for Coordinators of INTEGRATED PROJECTS (IP), Version 3: 11 March 2005 Ref. No. neg_200503_ip_en.doc, <http://www.cordis.lu/fp6/negotiation>

FP6, NEGOTIATION GUIDANCE NOTES for Coordinators of Specific Targeted Research PROJECTS (STREP) OR Specific Targeted INNOVATION PROJECTS (STIP), Version 3, 1 March, 2005 Ref. No. neg_200503_strp_en.doc, <http://www.cordis.lu/fp6/negotiation>

Institute of Standards and Technology (2003), Between Invention and Innovation, an Analysis of Funding for Early-Stage Technology Development, NIST GCR 02-841, Massachusetts, <http://www.atp.nist.gov/eao/gcr02-841/chapt2.htm>

Kline, S.J., N. Rosenberg (1986), "An Overview of Innovation", in Landau, R. and N. Rosenberg (eds.), The Positive Sum Strategy. Harnessing Technology for Economic Growth, National Academy Press, Washington, DC

OECD (1997), Oslo Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

OECD (2004), Compendium on Patent Statistics, OECD Publishing, Paris

Schumpeter, J. (1934), The Theory of Economic Development, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts

Szmytkowski Daniel (2005), Innovation Conceptualisation and Innovation New Models Theoretical Summary, Brussels

Annexes

Annex I

Extracting innovation definition criteria

Description of Work Annex I (Impact requirements)

INSTRUMENT	Potential Impact		
	Innovation Activities	Innovation Diffusion Process	Innovation Outcomes
Integrated Project (IP) <small>39</small>	Innovation-related activities (chapter 5) Research/innovation components (major elements or blocks of work). Describe each of these components; identify who will carry out each. Show the relevance and contribution of each of the participants to the project as a whole. (chapter 6A)	How the consortium will spread awareness and information about the project and its results beyond the research community with the public as a whole (chapter 5), (chapter 5.1), (chapter 5.2) plans for management of knowledge and intellectual property and a description of the use of results (further research or exploitation) and a plan for disseminating knowledge beyond the consortium during the lifetime of the project and afterwards. (chapter 6.5)	Relevance of the objectives of the IST priority/ activity objectives (chapter 4) Reinforcing competitiveness or on solving societal problems or addressing specific problems (chapter 5) Describe the added value (chapter 5)
Specific Targeted Research Project (STREP) <small>40</small>	Describe the innovation-related activities (chapter 5) scientific and technical (S&T) approach and provides in detail the work planned to achieve the objectives of the project for the full duration of the project (chapter 7) Research, technological development and innovation related activities (chapter 7)	How the consortium will spread awareness and information about the project and its results beyond the research community with the public as a whole (chapter 5) plan should cover the plans for management of knowledge and intellectual property and a description of the use of results (further research or exploitation), and a plan for disseminating knowledge beyond the consortium during the lifetime of the project and afterwards (chapter 6.2)	Reinforcing competitiveness or on solving societal problems or addressing specific problems (chapter 5) Describe the added value (chapter 5) Describe contributions to national or international standards, which may be made by the project, if any (chapter 5.1) significant impact the project may have on research or research-based policy development at regional, national or European level (5.1)

³⁹ FP6, NEGOTIATION GUIDANCE NOTES for Coordinators of INTEGRATED PROJECTS (IP), Version 3: 11 March 2005 Ref. No. neg_200503_ip_en.doc, <http://www.cordis.lu/fp6/negotiation>

⁴⁰ FP6, NEGOTIATION GUIDANCE NOTES for Coordinators of SPECIFIC TARGETED RESEARCH PROJECTS (STREP) OR SPECIFIC TARGETED INNOVATION PROJECTS (STIP), Version 3, 1 March, 2005 Ref. No. neg_200503_strp_en.doc, <http://www.cordis.lu/fp6/negotiation>

Annex II

Innovation Definition Analysis Framework

- SUBJECT:** measure for innovation character (determined by sector and type of organisation)
- PROCESS:** measure of degree of the innovativeness: radical character of the innovation
- OBJECT:** measure of the type of innovation – innovation deliverables
- TIMEFRAME:** measure of the innovation validity – time required to develop innovation
- OUTPUTS/RESULTS:** summarising all innovation process -quantified indicators for innovation effectiveness (I/O analysis)
- INPUTS:** measure of the resources engaged in innovation development (I/O analysis)

Annex III Statistical Results, Research Summary

				Innovation activities								Innovation (knowledge) Dissemination Process							
	Number of projects	average number of participators	average date of preparing technical annex	Technology creation and development	Research	Integrative activities	technological	scientific	organisational	commercial	financial	Cooperation	Publications, Press Releases, Reports, Workshops, Conferences	Electronic means eg. databases, websites, wide deployment of network applications	Commercial promotion (events, competitions)	Project patents, licensing, intellectual property protection	Importance of the network mechanisms in the innovation, addressed?	Open Source model	
IP	29	26	24/11/2003	21	16	8	24	11	9	4	0	20	20	18	6	3	9	3	
STP	17	10	15/10/2003	17	9	1	15	7	4	3	0	16	15	11	9	2	4	2	
TOTAL	46	20	8/11/2003	38	25	9	39	18	13	7	0	36	35	29	15	5	13	5	
percent of IP				72,4%	55,2%	27,6%	82,8%	37,9%	31,0%	13,8%	0,0%	69,0%	69,0%	62,1%	20,7%	10,3%	31,0%	10,3%	
percent of STP				100%	52,9%	5,9%	88,2%	41,2%	23,5%	17,6%	0,0%	94,1%	88,2%	64,7%	52,9%	11,8%	23,5%	11,8%	
percent of total				82,6%	54,3%	19,6%	84,8%	39,1%	28,3%	15,2%	0,0%	78,3%	76,1%	63,0%	32,6%	10,9%	28,3%	10,9%	
Results of the Innovation				Type of the Innovation: Object of the definition								Innovation characteristics			Subject (4) - Innovation recipient			Timeframe	
	Input to technical standards	Qualitative outcomes (e.g. diminishing digital divide, improved service quality)	(economic indicator change i.e.: job growth, GDP change, industrial production, demand/supply change)	Cost efficiency	Integration - synergies	Improved management/ organization	economic	social	Product or service	Process	Technology focused (TPP)	New product or process	Improvements in products or process	Extension/ extrapolation of existing technology: Extension/ efficiency study/ integration of existing technology	Market oriented	Social oriented	Is defined generally?	Defined	Average timeframe
IP	29	21	15	8	10	2	19	18	23	8	20	19	11	14	16	19	20	29	36
STP	17	13	8	5	2	1	13	11	16	3	15	12	8	11	9	11	10	17	30
TOTAL	46	34	23	13	12	3	32	29	39	11	35	31	19	25	25	30	30	46	34
percent of IP	100,0%	72,4%	51,7%	27,6%	34,5%	6,9%	65,5%	62,1%	79,3%	27,6%	69,0%	65,5%	37,9%	48,3%	55,2%	65,5%	69,0%	100,0%	
percent of STP	100,0%	76,5%	47,1%	29,4%	11,8%	5,9%	76,5%	64,7%	94,1%	17,6%	88,2%	70,6%	47,1%	64,7%	52,9%	64,7%	58,8%	100,0%	
percent of total	100,0%	73,9%	50,0%	28,3%	26,1%	6,5%	69,6%	63,0%	84,8%	23,9%	76,1%	67,4%	41,3%	54,3%	54,3%	65,2%	65,2%	100,0%	